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The role of thermal technologies for enhancing flexibility in Multi-Energy Systems through sector coupling: technical suitability and expected developments

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Abstract:

Thermal power generation technologies are widely used for electricity production, for heat provision in district or process heating systems, and for combined heat and power generation. In most cases thermal technologies are heat driven and electricity is produced as a by-product, thus resulting in a non-flexible behaviour of the electricity production. Modern power grids are characterized by an increasing share of renewable leading to a need for enhanced and flexible ways of controlling the power flow. In order to provide services to the power grid, thermal generating technologies may be used in a more efficient way, coupled to gas and heat storage systems or aggregated in virtual power plants. Several technical factors determine which technologies are suitable for flexibility provision, including: power-ranges, start-up times and ramp rates.

In this work, carried out in the frame of the MAGNITUDE H2020 project, the technical characteristics of thermal sector-coupling technologies were analysed using data from the seven real-life project's case studies. The technical suitability was determined based on the product requirements in selected European power markets for the provision of identified system services. Expected future developments and trends were as well highlighted.

1. Introduction

1.1. Need for more flexibility to operate the power network

The increasing share of volatile distributed resources, digitalization, increasing share of renewable energy (Fig.1) as well as the greater interconnection of heat, gas and power markets are the key drivers for the evolution of the power system. In recent years, it can be observed that production and demand patterns are becoming more erratic. To operate the power system in a reliable and secured manner, flexibility is required, e.g. to compensate coming fluctuations from renewables power generation or to respond to voltage or frequency deviations (Fig.2). As an example, thermal systems (power-to-heat, heat-to-power) may be utilized to overcome the oscillating behaviour of wind or solar production patterns as they are characterized by a higher inertia than electrical ones. [3] defines flexibility as “the ability to adjust generation or consumption in the presence of network constraints to maintain a secure system operation for reliable service to consumers”.

Needs of various needs of flexibility

Flexibility is required to address various grid management issues. Usually, a distinction is made between short term and long term flexibility needs:

- The first refers to the short term balance of energy supply and production for maintaining the stability of the power system (frequency containment on a national/regional level and voltage control at a more local level)
- The latter corresponds to the medium to long term equilibrium between supply and demand in energy systems characterized by high seasonal fluctuations due to a high penetration of renewable energy

resources, such as electricity from photovoltaic (PV) panels in the summer.

Fig. 1 Gross electricity production by fuel, TJ, EU-28, 2000-2016 [59]

Fig. 2 Renewable energy supply (in green) and power demand (in grey) in 2010 and 2050 [2]

Untapped potential of new flexibility options

Today, some conventional assets, such as gas turbines and pumped hydroelectric energy storage, that are able to react quickly to a grid issue, provide short-term flexibility to the power system while others, such as underground thermal energy storage, provide seasonal flexibility. However, with the advent of Smart Grids allowing for greater control of the energy assets, the roll-out of advanced metering infrastructure and storage technologies as well as the development of new market designs, additional alternatives for flexibility provision are to be considered. Those can be ranked in the following four categories as presented in [4]:

1. Demand-Side Measures (DSM): modification of consumer demand through price signals or behavioural change. The aim of DSM is to reduce demand during consumption peaks in order to avoid grid congestion issues or the ramp-up of additional power plants to meet growing demand
2. Electricity storage: electric batteries can be used to increase the self-consumption rate of PV-battery system at household level. Furthermore, bigger storage systems in the MW range installed nearby substations can help in maintaining grid stability through charging or discharging energy from or to the grid.
3. Supply-side measures: development of highly efficient and flexible Combined Heat and Power (CHP) technologies allows for increased provision of balancing energy. The curtailment (dispatch-down) of intermittent energy sources, such as wind and solar plants, is another supply-side option to tackle local congestions or system-wide issues.
4. Sector coupling technologies: technologies that allow conversion between heating/cooling, gas and electricity and can provide flexibility services to the power grid, such as heat pumps, electric boilers or Combined Cycle Gas Turbine (CCGT).

1.2 Objectives of the study

This paper investigates how to enhance flexibility provision in Multi-Energy Systems (MES) through sector coupling and heat storage technologies. The most promising

technologies in terms of flexibility provision are characterized and described according to key parameters such as power-ranges, start-up times and ramp rates to assess their capability to provide the most relevant system services. The assessment is based on a technical, economic and regulatory multi-criteria analysis with a focus on the West-European power markets. Finally, a discussion is given on current technology bottlenecks, future trends and drivers and electricity market boundaries.

The services considered in this document are presented briefly in the following table.

Table 1 Most relevant system services to be provided by Multi-Energy Systems [60]

Needs	Services	Short description
Frequency control and balancing	FCR (Frequency Containment Reserve)	Activated to stop a frequency deviation after the occurrence of an imbalance on the European synchronous network.
	aFRR (automatic Frequency Restoration)	Active power reserve, which is automatically activated to replace the FCR after a frequency deviation and to restore the frequency to its nominal value.
	mFRR (manual Frequency Restoration Reserve)	Active power reserve which is manually activated after a frequency deviation to complement or to release the aFRR if the demand for secondary control reserve is too high.
	RR (Replacement Reserve)	To provide an active power reserve which is manually activated to progressively restore the activated FRR and/or support FRR activation.
Energy trades	Day ahead energy trades/market	Trading of electricity for the following day. Biggest market volume.

Needs	Services	Short description
	Intraday energy trades/market	To trade on the short term energy volumes to be sold/purchased. Traded volumes currently increasing because of the development of intermittent energy generation.
System adequacy	Capacity requirement mechanisms	To contribute to the security of supply, avoid or postpone the unexpected accelerated shutdown of old conventional plants and compensate prolonged outages of crucial assets. Currently existing under very different forms in GB, FR, ES, SE and soon in IT.
Congestion management	Re-dispatching mechanisms or active power control	Measures taken when the forecasted or the real power flows exceed the physical capability of the grid components.

2. Main flexibility characteristics

2.1 Technology review

In the past, thermal technologies were installed mainly to produce heat and/or electricity [1]. Main focus was on combustion of fossil fuels coal, oil and natural gas. This had a big impact on the growth of efficiency of thermal generating technologies, firstly solid- and then liquid-fuel based ones. This increase of efficiencies was accompanied by an increase of size. However, due to growing role of renewables sources of energy, these trends have significantly slightly changed. Currently, besides being highly efficient (energetically and environmentally), technologies have to be very flexible and no longer large in terms of capacity, thus allowing them to play a key role in balancing power grid. Thermal power generation technologies are widely used for electricity production via steam processes, for heat provision in district or process heating systems, as well as combined heat and power (CHP) generation. The heat production is strongly coupled with heat demand, both for district and industrial uses. Thus resulting in a non-flexible behaviour for the electrical output. Therefore, power and heat production have to be decoupled to provide flexibility, e.g. it can be temporarily done by means of heat storage, electric boilers and heat pumps [5, 6, 7] in industrial and district heating (DH) networks. In addition to that, CHP should be operated in a full cogeneration mode to consider all electricity produced as a CHP-electricity, otherwise, non-CHP-electricity is generated. Full cogeneration mode means that units such as combined cycle gas turbines and steam condensing extraction turbines have to be operated with the total efficiency at least at 80%, and technologies such as steam back pressure turbines, gas turbines, internal combustion engines, micro turbines, Stirling engines, fuel cells, ORC have to reach threshold at least 75% of the total efficiency [61, 62]. Besides that an important value is power-to-heat ratio that is characteristic of each CHP unit and shows split between electricity from cogeneration and useful heat when operation in full cogeneration mode, it ranges from 0.45 for steam turbines to 0.95 for combined cycle gas turbine (CCGT) with heat recovery. It is clear that the units with low power-to-heat

ratio will be much more impacted by the flexible operation than those with higher values. Therefore, in future, not only efforts to utilise the surplus of heat generation (e.g. heat storage) shall be carried out, but also to maintain high efficiency a modular approach should be favoured.

Several factors determine which technologies are suitable for sector-coupling purposes, including: end-use and conversion energy efficiency, temperature levels that can be reached, possibility to bridge local energy demand with generation, environmental impact of the production and, not less importantly, value of the provided flexibility. Table 2 details the technologies, and related energy-conversion chains, that have been reviewed in this study.

Table 2 Selected sector coupling technologies [40]

#	Technology
Power consumption	
Power-to-Heat	
1	Heat pumps
2	Electrical boilers
Power-to-Cold	
3	Compression chillers
Power production	
Heat-to-Power	
4	Organic Rankine Cycle
5	Steam turbines
Gas-to-Power	
6	Gas engines
7	Gas turbines
Supporting technologies	
Storage	
8	Thermal storage:
Heat-to-Cold	
9	Sorption chillers

2.2 Power consumption

Heat pumps

Heat pumps (HPs) transfer heat from a low-temperature source (air-ambient or exhaust-, water- from the underground, lakes, rivers, seas, sewage treatment plants, or industrial processes and geothermal brine) to a higher-temperature sink. Applications are various: individual heating systems, district heating, tertiary and industrial applications, etc. HPs provide several units of heat per unit of electricity consumed, making them much more efficient than other Power-to-Heat (PtH) technologies [8], such as the electric boilers described hereafter. The thermal capacity of HPs ranges from 2 kWth for single-family houses to 30 MWth for integration in district heating and industrial processes. Heat pumps provide usually temperatures in the range 40-90 °C, but HPs development to provide higher temperatures is ongoing fast and some HPs providing heat in the temperature range 100 °C -160 °C and steam are already being tested and installed [9]. This development will broaden the field of application to many industrial processes and district heating networks running with superheated water [10]. If HPs are part of a multi-source heating system, e.g. heat storage and/or boilers, they cover the heat supply at least partially, and can be switched on or off according to the electricity grid

requirements. However, their flexibility potential is determined by the heat demand, or heat storage capability, of the overall heating system. HPs are usually not designed to switch on or off very often. Due to the mechanical parts inside the HP, too many start-ups/shut-downs increase abrasion and lower components (especially condensers and evaporators) lifetimes [11]. In the recent years, improvements have been done to run HPs more flexibly, e.g. via inverter technologies [12]. A major barrier to a wide deployment of heat pumps is the currently changing regulation on refrigerants. In more and more European countries, synthetic refrigerants based on fluorinated hydrocarbons are forbidden due to their strong Global Warming Potential (GWP) effects. Therefore, new low GWP refrigerants are developed, tested and applied in heat pumps, e.g. “fourth generation refrigerants” (e.g. hydrofluoroolefines), NH₃, CO₂ or natural carbohydrates (often flammable, toxic or requiring higher operating pressures). However, their thermodynamic properties differ compared to previously used refrigerants, which requires adaptation of compressors and exchangers to ensure the same performances [13]; so, further R&D efforts are needed.

Table 3 Technology Factsheet –Heat pump [40]

Parameter	Unit	Value
<i>Power output</i>	MWth	0.002-30
<i>Operating temperature level input</i>	°C	-20 - +50
<i>Operating temperature level output</i>	°C	30-100
<i>Minimum load</i>	%	10
<i>Controllable range</i>	%	10-100
<i>COP</i>	-	2-5 (practical) 1-20 (theoretical)
<i>Cold start up time</i>	min	300
<i>Hot start up time</i>	min	3
<i>Ramp rate up/down</i>	% nom power/ min	20
<i>Specific investment costs</i>	€/kWth	500-1 800

Electrical boilers

Two types of electric boilers are available, resistance and electrode ones. The resistance boilers are usually used in individual heating systems, whereas electrode boilers are only implemented for district heating (DH) due to their larger heat production capacities. Steam production for industry is also possible, but the specific costs increase significantly. There are no technical barriers which prevent the use of electrical boilers for flexibility services provision. The complexity of the power control is closely connected to the thermal capacity, due to the amount of heating elements. A minimum electrical load is required to enable very fast ramp-up times. Due to high electricity price compared to the low gas price, provision of base load heat via electric boilers is actually not economic so far. However, the flexible provision of heat is very common with electrode boilers, which are - due to their minimal pipework and no heating surfaces - very well suited to fast ramping. The response times to full nominal capacity are very fast; a minimum load of about 1% nominal capacity is required to keep the boiler operational. Electrode boilers can provide warm or hot water

as well as steam up to 300°C and 30 bar with efficiencies above 99% and capacities of 5-60 MW. The precise controllability, the fast load gradient and the fully automatically controllable operation make it possible to control all types of regulating power: primary, secondary up to minute reserve capacity. Therefore, electrical boilers as a mature technology, are well established in Scandinavia and Germany to support electrical grids coping with growing shares of intermittent wind & PV generation. In Denmark, large boilers are used predominantly for primary grid regulation; so, the whole capacity of the boiler is bid in for negative grid regulation thanks to the short ramp up times. In other countries, notably Germany, a market has developed for large electrode boiler in negative secondary regulation applications, i.e. absorbing power from the grid, but over longer periods. Small electric boilers are used to provide heat and domestic hot water for single and multi-family houses, but their sizes do not fit to market requirements for grid services provision unless aggregation is put in place.

Table 4 Technology Factsheet - Resistance heater and electrode boiler [40]

Boiler type		Resistance	Electrode
Parameter	Unit	Value	Value
<i>Power output</i>	MWth	0.005-10	5-60
<i>Operating temperature level input</i>	°C	10-110	10-110
<i>Operating temperature level output</i>	°C	30-140 (steam possible; but not common)	Water: 70-140 Steam: <300 at 45 bar
<i>Minimum load</i>	%	1	1-5
<i>Controllable range</i>	%	1-100	1-100
<i>Net Thermal Efficiency</i>	%	99	99
<i>Cold start up time</i>	Min	5 (but no common use)	5
<i>Hot start up time</i>	Min	<0.5	<0.5
<i>Ramp rate up/down</i>	% nom power/ min	100	100
<i>Specific investment costs</i>	€/kWe	30-150	40-100

Compression chillers

There are two types of chiller cycles: vapour compression and sorption. Sorption systems are thermally driven chillers; however, they are mainly used if surplus of non-expensive heat is available. Vapour compressors use reciprocating, screw or centrifugal compressors to supply the refrigerant circuit. Compressors are usually powered by electric motors, although they can also be driven by gas engines or steam turbines. Electrically driven chillers are the most popular systems to provide cold. Air-cooled compression chillers are available in sizes ranging from 0.1

up to 1 750 kWth and water-cooled chillers are available in sizes ranging from 21 to 21 000 kWth. Water-cooled units are more complex in installation and maintenance but they are smaller than the air-cooled units, which require outdoor location and whose efficiency is more affected by external conditions. In addition, water-cooled units have higher full and part-load efficiency. Compression chillers are mature technology with no major technical barriers [14]. Nevertheless, frequent compression cycles may result in increased system wear and temperature instability, which will lead to premature failures of the components. Short cycles may cause problems with lubrication, as there they do not let enough time for oil to circulate through the system.

Table 5 Technology Factsheet- Compression chiller [40]

Parameter	Unit	Air-cooled chillers	Water-cooled chillers
<i>Power output (cold output)</i>	kWth	0.1-1 750	21-21 000
<i>Operating temperature level output</i>	°C	-35 / +5	-45 / +5
<i>Minimum load</i>	%	20	20
<i>Controllable range</i>	%	20-100	20-100
<i>COP Cooling (EER)</i>	-	2.6-3.24	4.0-6.31
<i>Cold start up time</i>	min	20-60	20-60
<i>Ramp rate up/down (cooling)</i>	% nom power/min	1.6-5% for start up	1.6-5% for start up
<i>Specific investment costs</i>	€/ kWth	350 – 880	220 -530

2.3 Power Production

Steam turbines

Steam turbines are used to convert chemical energy of fuel into mechanical energy, which is used afterwards to move generators for electricity production. Power output range is up to 1900 MWe for nuclear power plants, up to 1 000 MWe for coal fired plants and up to 250 MWe for CHP units [15, 16 ,17]. Steam turbines are split into three main groups: condensing, backpressure and extraction ones. Depending on the size and design of a steam turbine, different isentropic efficiencies of the turbine are achievable: 53-57% for small single stage units, 60-67% for multistage units with power output < 10 MWe, and 75-90% for multistage turbines above 10 MWe. The flexibility of a steam turbine is impacted by the coupled steam generator, its combustion technology and fuel diet. Steam turbines are limited also by their cycling capability: on/off cycles are the main source of progressive deterioration of turbines material. Thermal and pressure stress applied cyclically accounts for the growth of existing flaws or incipient cracks, thus resulting in shortening the lifetime of turbine's and steam generator's components. To minimise the need for on/off operation, steam turbines should be run continuously taking into account the minimum allowed load. Therefore, their flexibility potential is mainly determined by partial load potential [18, 19, 20, 21, 22].

Table 6 Technology Factsheet- Single stage steam turbine [40]

Parameter	Unit	Single stage	
		Condensing	Backpressure
<i>Power output</i>	MWe	0.1-6	0.1-6
<i>Operating temperature level input</i>	°C	150-500	150-500
<i>Operating temperature level output</i>	°C	50-70	100-400
<i>Minimum load</i>	%	n.a.	n.a.
<i>Controllable range</i>	%	n.a.	n.a.
<i>Net Electrical Efficiency</i>	%	10-20	3-15
<i>Thermal Efficiency</i>	%	0	<80
<i>Cold start up time</i>	min	n.a.	n.a.
<i>Hot start up time</i>	min	n.a.	n.a.
<i>Ramp rate up/down</i>	% nom power/min	n.a.	n.a.
<i>Specific investment costs</i>	€/ kWe	1 100-1 500	

Table 7 Technology Factsheet- Multi stage steam turbine [40]

Parameter	Unit	Multi stage	
		Condensing	Backpressure
<i>Power output</i>	MWe	5-1 900	5-250
<i>Operating temperature level input</i>	°C	300-620	300-565
<i>Operating temperature level output</i>	°C	50-70	100-400
<i>Minimum load</i>	%	25-50	25-50
<i>Controllable range</i>	%	25/50-100	25/50-10
<i>Net Electrical Efficiency</i>	%	15-47	3-25
<i>Thermal Efficiency</i>	%	0	<80
<i>Cold start up time</i>	min	240-420	
<i>Hot start up time</i>	min	120-360	
<i>Ramp rate up/down</i>	% nom power/min	1-8%	
<i>Specific investment costs</i>	€/ kWe	1 100-1 500	

Current research activities focus on the development of advanced ultra-supercritical boilers that are to produce steam with parameters around 720 °C and 350 bar, thus increasing overall efficiency [23]. Besides the increase of efficiency, start-up time is also expected to be shortened (1-4 hours depending on starting condition) and systems should be more resistant to load change cycles and be able to provide ramping

rates at a level from 10%/10s to 10%/min. Achieving these goals will also require new plant control systems equipped with self-learning predictive systems [20].

ORC

Electricity can also be generated by Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) systems; turbines in which blades are moved by high molecular weight hydrocarbon organic substances. Their main advantage is that organic fluids have lower boiling points and higher vapour pressures compared to water thus offering a possibility to produce electricity from low-temperature sources. So, ORCs are widely used in applications using heat sources in the range of 70 - 530 °C [24, 25]. ORC systems are installed either as primary heat-to-power technology in bio/waste-fuelled CHPs, geo- and solar-thermal plants (up to 11 MWe of electrical output) or as a secondary hybrid technology to recycle waste heat streams (down to 5 kWe). The gross electrical efficiency for ORC turbines is between 5-26% and is highly linked with the temperature difference between heat source and heat output. Thermal efficiency represents the ratio between the amount of available heat output and the total energy input, and can reach up to 80%. In comparison to steam turbines, ORC systems maintain higher partial-load efficiency and can operate down to 10-15% of their nominal load. Start-up time for an ORC system is around 20-30 min, determined mainly by pressure and temperature stabilization after the start up. The ORC turbine may react to upward and downward regulation signals from the power grid with ramp rates up to 15-30%/min, but typical values are usually lower about 2 to 5% [26]. ORC units are typically designed for only one operating point, therefore part load-conditions are not optimal. Frequent start-ups of coupled engines will influence temperature and mass flow rate of the heat source, having a negative impact on the ORC performance. So, additional thermal storage for ORC systems may be required in order to avoid efficiency decrease and reduce the need of frequent starts and stops [27]. The ORC efficiency can also be improved by implementing an appropriate control strategy, which takes into account the variability of the heat source to achieve continuous re-optimization of operating conditions [28].

Table 8 Technology Factsheet- ORC [40]

Parameter	Unit	Value
<i>Power output</i>	MWe	0.05-11
<i>Operating temperature level input</i>	°C	60-530
<i>Operating temperature level output</i>	°C	60-252
<i>Minimum load</i>	%	10-15
<i>Controllable range</i>	%	10/15-100
<i>Net Electrical</i>	%	5.8-25.4
<i>Efficiency</i>		
<i>Thermal Efficiency</i>	%	≤80
<i>Cold start up time</i>	Min	20-30
<i>Hot start up time</i>	Min	15
<i>Ramp rate up/down</i>	% nom power/ min	15-30 2-5 (geothermal)
<i>Specific investment costs</i>	€/kWe	850 - 2 300

Gas engines

CHP units based on gas engines are used in commercial, industrial and institutional facilities usually in electricity-driven mode. Engines are offered in sizes from 10 kWe to 20 MWe in different variants: electricity only for base-load generation; electricity & heat for cogeneration / combined heat and power; electricity, heat and cooling water for tri-generation /combined heat, power and cooling [29, 30]. Gas engines are fuelled with either liquid or most common natural gas, which allows to start very quickly. Gas engines can be dispatched within minutes, full power achieved in less than 10 minutes compared to 30-45 minutes for combined cycle gas turbines. Operational ramp rate may achieve up to 50% of nominal power per minute and it can be even 100% for already started engines, which is an outstanding value compared to other technologies. In addition, gas engines may be aggregated into generating sets providing very high flexibility to the whole system, maintaining at the same time their high efficiency [31]. There are no major technical barriers for gas engines; they do not have minimum load limitations and thanks to the operation of the generating sets, they can maintain high efficiency at partial load. Very high ramp rates may be problematic, especially for large plants that are connected to high voltage grid due to the risk of the transformer overheating during cold start up [10].

Table 9 Technology Factsheet- Gas engine [40]

Parameter	Unit	Value
<i>Power output</i>	MWe	0.1-20
<i>Operating temperature level input</i>	°C	n.a.
<i>Operating temperature level output</i>	°C	365-465
<i>Minimum load</i>	%	30
<i>Controllable range</i>	%	30-100
<i>Net Electrical</i>	%	29.6-42
<i>Efficiency</i>		
<i>Thermal Efficiency</i>	%	35-53
<i>Cold start up time</i>	min	10-12
<i>Hot start up time</i>	min	0.5-2
<i>Ramp rate up/down</i>	% nom power/ min	20-50 (100 for already started engines)
<i>Specific investment costs</i>	€/kWe	800-1 450

Gas turbines

Gas turbines are applied for mobile or stationary power generators. Gas turbines are available in sizes from about 0.1 to almost 600 MWe, ranging from relatively small micro turbines to very large open or closed cycle gas turbines used for power generation in central stations [32]. For CHP applications, gas turbines typically have sizes greater than 5 MWe and they provide high temperature exhaust gases that can be used either to generate high-pressure steam, hot water or chilled water when they are coupled with absorption chillers. Hot gases can be also used directly in industrial applications for heating or drying. The electrical generation efficiency of gas turbines varies between 25 and 62.22% [33]; very high efficiencies are achieved for combined cycle gas

turbines. Nevertheless, efficiency is highly impacted by partial load operation, declining as the load decreases. In addition, the load affects not only the efficiency but also the emissions, which increase when lowering the power output. This load is around 50-60% for CCGT heavy-duty turbines (even if, by optimizing the system, it can be reduced to 30-40% [34]), around 25-40% for simple cycle turbines and 5-18% for aero-derivative turbines. For hot start conditions, the start-up time for combined cycle gas turbine is about 30-45 minutes, for simple cycles it is about 10-15 minutes and less than 5 minutes for aero-derivative units. Ramping rates can reach up to 6%/min for CCGT; 7.5-16.3%/min for Simple Cycle Gas Turbines (SCGT) and 40-132%/min for the aero-derivative turbines [35, 10]. Furthermore, fluctuating loads and an increased number of start-ups will reduce lifetime of gas turbines, thus resulting in higher maintenance costs [36].

Table 10 Technology Factsheet- Gas turbine [40]

Parameter	Unit	Simple cycle combustion heavy & duty	Simple cycle Aero-derivative	Combined cycle combustion
Power output	MWe	3-593	36-117	44-593
Operating temperature level input	°C	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Operating temperature level output	°C	365-465	430-530	Hot water or steam depending on the pressure 30-60
Minimum load	%	25-40	5-18	
Controllable range	%	25/40-100	5/18-100	30/60-100
Net Electric Efficiency	%	23-40	32-42	52-62
Thermal Efficiency	%	44-50	44-50	33-38
Cold start up time	min	10-45	10-12	145-255
Hot start up time	min	5-15	5	30-45
Ramp rate up/down	% nom power/min	7.5-16.3	82-132	5.2-6
Specific investment costs	€/kWe	375- 1 130	960 - 1 330	545-595

2.4. Supporting technologies

Heat storage

In Multi-Energy Systems, electricity production and consumption are often coupled with the supply of heat. The coupled production is usually driven by customer heat needs, which lowers the degrees of freedom for variable electricity production. Therefore, a flexibility increase on the electricity side requires the decoupling of the heat demand from heat supply of cogeneration and PtH units. Thermal Energy Storage (TES) enables decoupling, e.g. electricity production from CHP units can be increased if heat surplus is

stored; vice versa, CHP electricity production can be decreased if the related heat demand is covered by previously stored heat or alternative heat sources. For electricity consumption in PtH units, similar considerations arise. Thermal storage is about 100 times cheaper than electricity; so, use of TES will grow due to increasing volatile RES in the electricity mix. TES stores either warm or hot water as well as steam. Hot water tank sizes range from some 100 dm³ for single buildings to 50 000 m³ for large DH networks. The corresponding capacities in MWh depend on the temperature differences and on the temperature levels of the entire heating system [37]. Typically, the sizing is done to provide the maximum heat demand for at least some hours to several days; resulting in a range of 30-50% of the heat peak load as the optimum storage size. Therefore, capacities in terms of stored energy can achieve more than 2 000 MWh in large DH networks [38]. TES efficiency corresponds to heat losses over time, depending mainly on the thickness of the insulation. Larger tanks are more efficient thanks to the better surface-to-volume ratio. Mean values for the specific heat loss are around 10 W/m², or about 0.2% of capacity per day. Steam accumulators are used in industrial steam networks, usually to cover steam peak demands in batch processes, and as a back-up system instead of auxiliary boilers. In such industrial processes, steam has to be delivered with constant quality within some minutes for at least 15 minutes. If the dimensioning of the steam accumulator and the CHP unit producing steam is appropriate, steam storage can – similarly to hot water tanks – contribute to the decoupling of power production and steam demand. The storage capacities are usually in the range of several MWh, but new developments are broadening the capacities into the GWh range by cascading units.

3. Technical suitability and expected developments

3.1 Technical suitability to services

In the previous chapter, widely used key technologies have been characterized in terms of their flexibility. Three parameters are particularly the most important when considering flexibility provision:

- Ramp-rate, expressed in units of power over time, indicates how quickly a power plant output can be adjusted up or down to meet growing or decreasing demand. Some technologies such as gas turbines are more flexible than others and serve usually as peaking units because they can be ramped up and down quickly to compensate sudden changes in supply or demand.
- Start-up time, expressed in units of time, represents the time needed by a power plant to reach full load. A distinction is made between (i) cold start when the power plant is switched on at a low temperature relative to its normal operating temperature, (ii) hot start referring to a start occurring when the state of the plant is close to its normal operating temperature.
- The power output, expressed in units of power that refers to the nominal power generation. The crucial point for this parameter is the capacity size; often, the flexible capacity does not fit to the market and net provider requirements. To reach higher

capacities some power plants can be pooled together. Virtual power plants (VPP) consists of a central IT control system aggregating the capacities of several homogeneous or heterogeneous distributed energy resources. This aggregation concept allows to achieve greater economy through economies of scale and reduce the complexity for market participants [41].

In Table 11, the above flexibility parameters such as power output, start-up time and ramp rate of selected technologies are summarized. It can be observed that the figures vary a lot from one technology to another one and even that within the same technology class there may be large differences between minimal and maximal values (e.g. this is particularly true for simple cycle gas turbines with power ratings ranging from 3 to almost 600 MWe and hot start-up times between 105 and 45 minutes).

Start-up times

Some technologies such as steam turbines and CCGT require up to several hours to reach their nominal power after a cold start while other such as gas engines, e-boilers and aero-derivative turbines can be switched on in less than 15 minutes. To reduce the time needed to react to a grid issue and provide reserve capacity quickly, some units can be held in hot reserve. Thus, reaction time can be reduced by more than a half and technologies may be eligible to participate in certain balancing markets. As shown in Table 11, gas engines when maintained in hot reserve can provide full power after some seconds but need several minutes to reach full capacity after long standstill periods.

According to a recent report of the International Energy Agency (IEA), European countries such as Denmark, Italy and Germany have deployed strategies to improve flexibility particularly of coal-fired and CCGT power plants [39]. For example, the thermal power plant fleet in Germany has been upgraded to be able to start and stop twice a day in response to higher flexibility requirements.

Power outputs

Heat pumps, e-boilers and chillers are characterized by a small power output. These smaller units may be aggregated to form larger volumes in order to meet market entry conditions if approved by national authorities (aggregation of small size power plants is still not allowed in Spain and Italy).

The aggregation of heat pumps for the provision of reserve in power systems has been demonstrated in several Smart Grid pilots [42, 43, 44]. However, the lack of a standard for the control interface/management of demand control solutions is seen as one of the major technological obstacle to the uptake of such residential demand response programs [45].

The flexibility provided by some smaller units is already used in some countries. German and Swiss DSOs introduced specific heat pump tariffs and remote control mechanism to limit the active power of these units during certain period of time when energy demand is high. As compensation, participating customers benefit from a significant reduction in network charges in their electricity bill [46, 47]. France also introduced a Time Of Use (TOU) electricity tariff especially designed for customers using electric water heaters to produce domestic hot water. These heaters are switched on at night when the energy demand is at its lowest [48]. Furthermore, the NiceGrid pilot project demonstrated that electric water heaters can absorb excess local photovoltaic production, thus contributing to voltage stability in low voltage lines characterized by high PV production and low demand [49].

Ramp rates

Another important feature of any generation asset in the light of flexibility procurement is its ramp rate – the rate at which a plant can decrease or increase its output to compensate fluctuations in supply and demand. According to [50], due to the increasing share of fluctuating energy sources, up to 30% of the feed-in of the national thermal generation capacities in Germany, France, Spain and Italy will need to ramp-up or down by 2030. As presented in Fig.3, simple cycle aero-derivative turbines and electric boilers are characterized by a high ramp rate. These two features make them particularly suitable for the provision of fast frequency response services. However, power plant cycling operations may lead to component damages, loss in efficiency and more operation-related emissions as well as higher operating and maintenance costs since most of the plants are designed to run as baseload plants around the clock [51]. As highlighted by [39], regulatory modifications and the introduction of economic incentives for plant operators may be needed to unlock the flexibility of thermal plants especially the large ones.

Table 11 Main technical characteristics of the considered technology [40]

Technology	Power output/input	Hot start up time	Cold start up time	Ramp rate
	MWe	min	min	% of nom. power/min
<i>Steam turbines</i>	1-1000	120-360	240-420	1-8%
<i>ORC turbine</i>	0.05-11	15	20-30	15-30%
<i>Gas engine*</i>	0.1-20	0.5-0.2	10-20	20-50%*
<i>Gas turbine simple cycle</i>	3-593	5-15	10-45	8-16%
<i>Gas turbine combined cycle</i>	44-593	30-45	145-255	6%
<i>Heat pump**</i>	0.0005-7.5	3	300	20%
<i>E-boiler</i>	0.005-60	0.5	5	100%
<i>Chillers***</i>	0.0002-14	3	30-60	6%

*- running gas engine may have ramp rate of 100%/min; **- power consumption calculated for COP=4; ***- power consumption calculated for COP=6.5, hot start up time as for heat pumps; ****- only thermal power is shown

Fig. 4 Ramp rates [% nom.power/min and MW/min] and of hot start-up time [min] of selected coupling technologies (data correspond to largest existing units) [40]

To summarize, it appears that coupling technologies with short ramp-up and start-up times such as e-boilers, gas engines and simple cycle aero-derivative gas turbines meet requirements for frequency containment reserve markets. However, e-boiler cannot provide more electricity to the grid unlike gas based units. Simple cycle and combined cycled gas turbines and aggregated heat pumps/chillers and ORC systems are suited for the participation in the short-term energy balancing markets. Sector coupling technologies with less flexible capabilities such as condensing turbines and steam turbines cannot provide the full range of flexibility services. They seem to be most relevant for intraday and day ahead energy markets. Heat and gas storage can increase the flexibility provision of the above-mentioned technologies or system configurations to which they are coupled or in which they are integrated. It can be seen that fast ramps, and short start-up times are given by small capacities, therefore it may be necessary to aggregate them in order to provide services to the market. However, it must be noted that market rules vary

from one country and the strategy to be adopted will depend largely on the local power system's condition.

Fig.4 shows the investment cost of reactivity which is a result of dividing specific costs of investment by ramp rates. Values vary between 0.3 for e-boilers up to 375 for solid fuel steam turbines and indicate that, among the examined technologies, only a few of them - such as e-boilers, gas aero-derivative turbines and gas engines - can provide flexibility to an electricity market or to a local multi energy system (peak load units) with a lower investment cost compared to another technologies, for which the flexibility provision shall be targeted only as a by-product and a decision about the investment should not be based only on this purpose. Of course, besides the investment costs, operational costs are as well of key importance and are influenced by efficiency, fuel price, environmental costs, maintenance, electricity costs, etc. Hybridization, e.g. coupling gas engines with e-boilers, may not only increase the capability of the multi-energy system to provide flexibility to the electricity system, but also minimize the operational costs and/or increase the incomes.

Fig. 3 Cost-of-reactivity- Specific cost of investment divided by ramp rates for different technologies ([€/kW]/[% of nom. power/min]) [40]

From a technology coupling perspective, thermal storage is necessary: even though it does not directly provide flexibility to the electricity markets, it enables to decouple electricity and heat production, which is important to maintain high overall efficiency.

3.2 Major trends and expected developments of the energy system in the European Union

The energy system and power, heat and gas markets undergo a transformation driven by rapid growth of renewables, higher energy efficiency thanks to more stringent regulations, digitalization and electrification in the cooling, heating and transport sectors. The major trends and developments identified in the EU reference scenario 2016 with projections until 2030 for the selected sector coupling technologies are as detailed in the following paragraphs [52]. A moderate increase in efficiency, combined with a decrease in costs, can however be assumed for all considered technologies.

However, as stated in [67], the decentralisation of power generation from RES, sector coupling and digitalisation increasingly expose *the energy system to cyberattacks and incidents, which may jeopardise the security of energy supply*. Energy network operators and relevant stakeholders will have then to make sure to follow the available recommendations on real-time requirements, cascading effects and combination of legacy and state-of-the-art technology to reduce and control the cybersecurity risks. These include, for example: splitting the overall systems into logical zones to enable the application of suitable cybersecurity measures, establish design criteria and an architecture for a resilient grid, and establish an automated monitoring and analysis capability for security-related events.

Power-To-Heat

The steam and heat demand in the EU28 is expected to remain approximately stable throughout the projection period. In the long term e-boilers and heat pumps penetrate the district heating market and increase their market share while solid and gaseous fuels see their share reduced. For heat pumps and refrigeration units, the biggest challenge is the upcoming ban on the use of fluorinated gases (F-gases) as refrigerants. The use of environmentally friendly alternatives may affect performance and the cost of future deployed technologies. Regarding electric boilers, it is expected that sales of small heaters (also called “boosters”) will increase because the use of an additional energy source (electricity) is often needed for domestic hot water preparation in low temperature district heating networks and heating systems [53]. Furthermore, high temperature heat pumps are likely to increase in importance in the future because their potential contribution to efficiency improvement of base load CHP plant connected to DH networks and can be used to produce steam at local consumption point for industrial processes instead of fossil fuels [54]. Generally speaking, it can be said that steam will be produced more and more by Power-to-Heat technologies, but also from natural gas and biofuels, and less from other fossil energy sources.

Power-To-Cold

The demand for air conditioning will increase because cooling degree days are assumed to augment. Thus, more chillers will be rolled-out in the residential sector. These

small units can be aggregated to collectively address grid issues [55]. According to [56], space cooling is responsible for a significant portion of EU electricity consumption in households (~5%) and in the tertiary sector (~13%). This market is characterized by a strong growth potential, particularly in households.

Heat-to-Power

The conversion of heat to electricity via ORC systems is gaining in importance. Especially waste to heat recovery is an emerging field for ORC with an interesting potential for all unit sizes ranging from medium to large size plants recovering heat from gas turbines, internal combustion engines or industrial processes [57]. From a technological point of view, the development of high-temperature materials is necessary to recover heat from sources with increasingly high temperatures. Similarly to heat pumps, ORC systems can improve the efficiency of the Power-to-Heat technologies to which they are coupled, resulting in a very load-flexible power plant with optimal part load efficiency and compliance with emission standards.

Gas-to-power

Gas-fired generation slightly increases due to the role that gas is playing as a back-up technology for intermittent renewable sources. The majority of investments are in CCGT plants used for flexibility and reserves. The share of Combined Heat and Power (mainly fuelled with gas and biomass) will increase following the general trend towards highly efficient power plants. It is also expected that the global gas engine market will grow, especially for the units sized between 400 kWe and 20 MWe. Key drivers for this development are falling oil and gas prices and ambitious renewable energy targets [58].

Besides that, due to very high electrical (up to 60%) and overall efficiency (up to 85-95%) fuel-cell based cogeneration may play big role in the future CHP systems [63, 64, 71].

Fig. 5 Cumulative Global Deployment of Large-Scale (>200 kWe) Fuel Cells /MW [68]

Figure 5 shows that the global installed capacity of fuel cells has increased more than ten times in recent years. In the US, some units have a capacity up to 6 MWe and are used in commercial buildings [65], South Korea is becoming a key player for fuel cells deployment with the biggest fuel-based CHPs in the world [69, 70]. On the other hand, Japan is very active when it comes to micro-CHPs what is proven by almost 300 000 already installed residential units [71]. Nevertheless, further research and development are still required to deal with some technical challenges to lower down the investment costs and increase their lifetime and flexibility [66]. Besides natural gas, they can be fuelled both with hydrogen and biogas, which may help to decarbonize the heat and power production.

Heat storage

The EU Reference Scenario does not take into account supporting technologies such as heat and gas storages. However, it can be assumed that hot water tanks and steam accumulators will play a key role to compensate daily, weekly and seasonal fluctuations in heat demand, as well as a more flexible CHP performance. Combined with other coupling technologies such as e-boilers, heat storages can provide additional flexibility to the power system and support the integration of renewable energy resources. New steam storage systems are expected to offer significant cost and performance benefits. (Bio-)Gas storages will remain a niche market that will mainly serve to exploit flexibility in industrial sites where gas production or demand is important.

Conclusion

As presented in this document, sector coupling technologies, which are becoming increasingly more and more important due to the penetration of distributed resources and the digital transformation can provide flexibility to the power system. An analysis carried out for selected technologies shows that their capabilities to provide system services are mainly dependent on technical flexibility features such as power output, ramp-rate and hot/cold start time, which has also to fit and to the characteristics of the flexibility products (minimum volume, eligible technologies) that may differ a lot from one country to another. In particular, gas-fuelled units (e.g. turbines, engines) appear to be the most promising solutions for flexibility provision, thanks to their technological characteristics, modularity and cost-effectiveness. Thermal systems can be supported on the other hand by electric boilers and heat storage, for effectively decouple heat demand and production, while maintaining high production efficiency. Thanks to the development in terms of lifetime and costs, fuel cells are expected to become a reliable solution for small-scale cogeneration in the next decade.

However, not only technical factors are vital for the provision of flexibility services, but also the economic ones. According to [39], many existing generators are inflexible from an economic standpoint of view because of must-run requirements and performance-based regulations. The steps to be taken to unleash the flexibility potential of sector coupling technologies is strongly dependent on local grid conditions. Nevertheless, there are some general guidelines to follow to enhance power system's flexibility. Firstly, it is crucial to assess accurately and regularly the flexibility

requirements of a given country or balancing area and determine the flexibility potential that can be provided by specific coupling technologies. In a second step, policy actions such as the revision of inflexible contract terms, the development of innovative market design and the creation of fair compensation for flexibility provision will be required. The Horizon 2020 MAGNITUDE project that aims at developing business and market mechanisms, as well as supporting coordination tools to provide flexibility to the European electricity system will help tackle some of these challenges.

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